

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Global validation report

DELIVERABLE 1.3

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

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Global validation report

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Abstract

This deliverable provides a global validation report. It is based on the individual WPs in which the deliverables and milestones were processed. Validation is carried out on the basis of the objectives underlying each WP, deviations (if any) from the initial planning are mentioned and explained.

The global validation report is based on the first and second technical reports of the OPERAS-PLUS project, which were prepared by the Consortium respectively at the end of the first period (From M1 to M12) and second period (From M13 to M36) of the project and which detail the work carried out for each Work Package and the main deviations

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of tasks planning. Thus the global validation report incorporates the elements of these two technical reports, but articulates these elements for each task in order to show the progress of the work between the first and the second period of the project.

Contents

Glossary	5
I. Executive Summary	6
II. The OPERAS-PLUS project	7
A. Objectives	7
III. Explanation of the work carried out per WP	8
A. Work Package 1: Coordination and management	8
Deviations	9
Explanation of the work carried out per task	9
B. Work Package 2: OPERAS construction phase framework development	10
Deviations	11
Explanation of the work carried out per task	12
C. Work Package 3: Member States / Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement	13
Deviations	13
Explanation of the work carried out per task	13
D. Work Package 4: OPERAS Innovation Lab development	14
Deviations	15
Explanation of the work carried out per task	15
E. Work Package 5: Technical Support to OPERAS Services	16
Deviations	16
Explanation of the work carried out per task	17
F. Work Package 6: User Engagement and Training	18
Deviations	18
Explanation of the work carried out per task	19
G. Work Package 7: Support to National Nodes	19
Deviations	20
Explanation of the work carried out per task	20
H. Work Package 8: Communication and Impact Assessment	21
Deviations	22
Explanation of the work carried out per task	23
IV. Impact	26

Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AoC	OPERAS Assembly of the Commons
CFAO	Chief Finance and Administration Officer
EA	OPERAS Executive Assembly
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GA	OPERAS General Assembly
KER(s)	Key Exploitable Results
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OPERAS	open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
OPERAS AISBL	Legal structure incorporated in Belgium and coordinating OPERAS
OPERAS Central Hub	OPERAS AISBL + OCT
OPERAS National Nodes	Institutions representing OPERAS AISBL in their respective countries
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG(s)	OPERAS Special Interest Group(s)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

I. Executive Summary

OPERAS-PLUS is a project of particular importance for the development of OPERAS AISBL and OPERAS as a research infrastructure, which has been in the Construction Phase of becoming an ERIC since 2022. The results of this project will contribute directly to the OPERAS research infrastructure in its transformation.

What makes OPERAS-PLUS special is that the results are always placed in the context of OPERAS AISBL. This requires a close relationship with the governing bodies and structures of the research institutions for which OPERAS-PLUS works and which are to benefit from this project. It was therefore never the aim to establish OPERAS-PLUS as a separate brand. Rather, this project has always had a supporting and serving function for the research infrastructure itself. The project pursued this goal with an approach based on two pillars: one focus on the further development of the infrastructure as a legal entity, and the other on consolidating the service catalogue.

These goals have had a particular influence on the dynamics of the project. It applies to the close exchange with the representatives and functionaries of OPERAS, but also with policy makers and representatives of the national ministries, which have influenced individual project phases and the work in various WPs.

In particular, this applied to WP1, whose main task was the coordination and day-to-day management of the WPs. In addition, there was corresponding coordination with the coordinators of OPERAS AISBL and the governing bodies, especially the Executive Assembly. External factors also influenced the work on the legal framework and long-term strategies, which were part of WP2. Current political developments have had a direct impact on the work on the deliverables that were the focus here. The same can be said for WP3, which dealt with cooperation between the OPERAS bodies and coordinated the various Special Interest Groups. The aim of WP7 was to promote and establish (further) the National Nodes and improve their connection to the central hub of OPERAS in order to link the European and national communities. The harmonisation of organisational structures between the National Nodes and OPERAS AISBL also made an important contribution to the development of the ERIC.

With the Innovation Lab, WP4 laid an important foundation for the future viability of OPERAS Research Infrastructure by addressing the community's needs for new services. At the same time, methodological approaches were implemented to systematically shape innovation. All of this was done in a very practice-oriented manner. OPERAS AISBL already offers a range of services. WP5 was tasked with further developing these services in line with FAIR principles to ensure their sustainability. The service portfolio established and further consolidated here is central to the OPERAS community. WP6 followed up on this and investigated the acceptance of the services offered from the users' perspective. Of particular importance for this WP was the

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development of a methodologically sound evaluation based on user experience. Finally, the provision of a system of training content for the best possible use of the services was also part of the project.

WP8 accompanied these dynamic developments by monitoring and adapting the communication structures. This ensured that the necessary information was available to all bodies and stakeholders involved in a timely and appropriate manner.

Overall, it became apparent that OPERAS-PLUS advanced the fundamental goal of transforming the OPERAS AISBL research infrastructure into an ERIC. The individual WPs successfully carried out their tasks at various levels to achieve this goal.

II. The OPERAS-PLUS project

A. Objectives

The overarching goal of the OPERAS-PLUS project was derived from the development of the OPERAS research infrastructure, which is preparing to obtain ERIC status and has been in the construction phase since 2022. Four specific objectives were identified as part of the ongoing preparations for the formation of an ERIC. These objectives also played a decisive role in shaping the WPs, ensuring the further development of OPERAS with regard to ERIC status. Specifically, these were the following objectives:

- (1) The first priority was to consolidate the general administrative structure of OPERAS. This included financial and legal aspects, but also issues of personnel development. Linked to this was the requirement to better structure the various bodies and offices of the research infrastructure and to better coordinate and network their activities. The first topic was addressed by WP1, while the second was taken up by WP3, with both WPs working closely together.
- (2) The second specific objective was the further development of the OPERAS National Nodes. Existing National Nodes were to be stabilised, and planned nodes were to be supported in their development. A key requirement was to better link the nodes to the central hub of OPERAS. This task was taken on by WP7.
- (3) The third specific objective focused on the services offered by OPERAS. On the one hand, the service catalogue was to be reorganised, and existing services were to be further developed and, if not already done, fully developed in all functionalities. The growing range of these services also required a corresponding monitoring system to ensure the management and further development of the portfolio. Finally, the development of new services was to be more strategically aligned with current developments, but above all with the needs of the scientific communities. Accordingly, there was a need for an

innovation lab that would steer precisely these future developments and make them usable for OPERAS. WP5 was responsible for setting up the service portfolio, while WP4 was responsible for the innovation lab.

- (4) Finally, a fourth specific objective aimed to better anchor OPERAS in the European Research Area, which also included the further integration of new members and countries. This requirement was fundamentally in line with the communication and dissemination efforts, which were primarily supported by WP8. WP6, which was dedicated to user engagement and training, was also intended to promote the external impact and further dissemination of OPERAS services.

It would be wrong to assume that only the individual WPs assigned here supported the four specific objectives and promoted their respective purposes. Rather, the project dynamics showed a consistently cross-WPs effect, so that all activities in the WPs benefited the individual objectives and the overarching goal of further preparation for the ERIC.

III. Explanation of the work carried out per WP

Note: The explanations of the individual tasks in the WPs do not distinguish between the two reporting periods (M1-M12 and M13-M36), as the vast majority of activities were carried out across this boundary. Where necessary, the exact durations of measures in the tasks are specified individually.

A. Work Package 1: Coordination and management

The WP organised the day-to-day running of the project, ensuring that the work plan was implemented in accordance with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. This included formal project planning, which ensured that the various deliverables were completed on time. It was important to ensure a smooth exchange of information between the coordinator and the WPs, but also between the WPs themselves. This also included administrative tasks, particularly in the financial area, to ensure the correct management of the budget. Regular reports to the EC and communication with the EU Project Officer were also part of the proper project workflow. In line with the specific purpose of the project, which was to further support the OPERAS AISBL research infrastructure, coordination with the OPERAS committees and its officials was also particularly important.

WP leader: MWS.

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Contributors: AMU, OPERAS, UNIZD, Jisc, IBL PAN, UC.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D1.1: Rules and procedures including monitoring and evaluation processes and risk and quality management plan

D1.2: Data Management Plan (DMP)

D1.3: Global validation report

Milestone:

MS1 Consortium virtual kick-off meeting

Deviations

From M1-M12:

The D1.2 “Data Management Plan (DMP)”, being due on 28 February 2023, has been submitted 13 March 2023. The delay did not affect the ongoing activities in the project. Withdrawal of CNRS as project partner, its tasks and responsibilities assigned to AMU (settled in AMD01)

From M13-M36. No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 1.1 – Administrative, financial, and legal management

If OPERAS-PLUS were to promote the further development of OPERAS, the project would benefit in turn from the existing research infrastructure structures. This was also important because all project partners were already familiar with these formats. Collaborative platforms were therefore used for general project work, so that minutes could be taken at meetings and information could be viewed and edited immediately by all project partners.

Familiarity with this framework also facilitated the withdrawal of CNRS as a project partner. Its tasks in the project were taken over by AMU, which was easily arranged without delaying the progress of the project. This process, along with reassigned finances and renaming deliverables (and merging two of them: D2.1 and D2.2), was part of the first amendment (AMD01) which was initiated 7 July 2023 and accepted 14 November 2023.

Task 1.2 – Day-to-day management

Day-to-day operations quickly fell into place thanks to regular meetings held by the WPs themselves to organise their tasks. However, the monthly Work Package Leaders' Meetings were important for ensuring the exchange of information between the WPs. Above all, this helped to prevent the individual tasks from becoming

compartmentalised. The regularity of the meetings also made it easier to respond to the unique dynamics of the project. In some cases, it became apparent that it made sense to postpone deliverables in order to ensure that the results were as mature as possible. These processes were identified at an early stage and could therefore be clarified with the EC. Similarly, the well-established information and exchange structures meant that there was hardly any loss of expertise when there were personnel changes among the project partners. New colleagues were quickly brought up to speed with the work processes. The meetings and consultations took place predominantly online. However, as many project partners were also represented in the OPERAS Executive Assembly (EA) and many representatives of OPERAS-PLUS met during face-to-face meetings of the OPERAS committees, these meetings could often be used to clarify questions relating to this project.

Task 1.3 – Reporting and administration

Reporting followed the 'Rules and procedures including monitoring and evaluation processes and risk and quality management plan' (D1.1), which in turn benefited from examples from previous projects, especially OPERAS-P. Quality assurance through appropriate review processes was particularly helpful in ensuring the consistency of deliverables. Both technically qualified representatives of the project partners and external experts were involved in this process. The proven EU-Fin system was used for financial management, which enabled clear budget management of the project funds. The procedure also worked very well in conjunction with the administrations of the other project partners.

Task 1.4 – Data Management Plan (DMP)

The DMP, which was already due for M6, was an important prerequisite for the work of other WPs. It was particularly relevant for the exploitation and dissemination plan (D8.3). The DMP was generally based on preliminary work from previous projects, especially OPERAS-P, and it was monitored and kept up to date throughout the project.

B. Work Package 2: OPERAS construction phase framework development

The WP focused on developing a sustainable governance structure for OPERAS. This was done with the close involvement of ministry representatives, as many of whom as possible were included in the processes and discussions. As a result, a strategy for the research infrastructure was presented that reorganises the governance of OPERAS in preparation for the ERIC. In addition, corresponding frameworks for financial planning were developed, based on several scenarios to ensure the planned transition to ERIC status. This was accompanied by an updated business model and further strategy papers on human resources and risk management. All these considerations were made in close consultation with the OPERAS committees, which is why coordination with WP3, which was to support the committees, was very close within the project itself.

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WP leader: OPERAS.

Contributors: MWS, AMU, OPERAS, UNIZD.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D2.1: OPERAS legal & governance framework, financial & business model framework and Strategy Implementation Plan (according to AMD01 new deliverable merging the former D2.1 and D2.2)

D2.3: OPERAS pan-European Human Resources Policy

D2.4: OPERAS Risk Management Framework and Capacity Plan

D2.5: OPERAS Governance Framework & Strategy Implementation Plan - Update

D2.6: OPERAS pan-European Human Resource Policy - Final

D2.7: OPERAS Risk management framework & Capacity plan

D2.8: OPERAS Legal & Governance Framework, Financial & Business Model Framework and Strategy Implementation Plan – Final

Milestone:

MS5: Presentation of the Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan to the GA and Member States and Associated Countries representatives

Deviations

From M1-M12:

D2.1 “OPERAS legal & governance framework, financial & business model framework & and Strategic Implementation plan – Initial” was originally due on 31 Aug 2023. Being part of the AMD01 it has been merged with D2.2 and renamed. In the course of this rearrangement it was submitted on 6 November 2023.

D2.3 “OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy” was initially due on 31 March 2023 and has been postponed to 31 August 2023 (AMD01). The delay of nearly one month (submission on (27 September 2023) resulted from finalising the document properly, as legal questions required more inquiries than expected. The delay did not affect the progress of the project.

From M13-M36:

D2.4 “OPERAS risk management framework and capacity plan” was due on 30 November 2023. It finally was submitted on 31 May 2024. The reason for this delay were the ongoing consultations with ministries and the (newly emerging) BGR respectively which were deemed necessary to take into account for this deliverable.

D2.7 “OPERAS risk management framework and capacity plan – final” was due on 31 May 2025. Its submission was delayed for some days (4 June 2025) without any affect to the project.

D2.6 OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy – Final, being an update of D2.3 was initially due on 28 February 2025 and has been postponed to 28 June 2025. It has

finally been submitted on 13 August 2025. The reason for this delay was to align this document with the neighbouring deliverables D2.7, D2.8 and D2.9.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 2.1 – Governance of OPERAS

The focus was on the fundamental revision of OPERAS' governance, which includes the internal structure of the research infrastructure and its committees. The main focus here was on issues relating to the reorganisation of the membership structure. The involvement of ministerial participation, which resulted in the concept of the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR), was also of great importance. Task 2.1 was therefore closely linked to Task 2.2, as were the following tasks. This thematic link also resulted in the early decision to reorder the deliverables (see D2.1 above and its update D2.8).

Task 2.2 – Legal and financial framework

Closely linked to the redesign of governance was the question of the financial basis for maintaining and operating OPERAS. Accordingly, a draft business model was developed based on the previous cost model. Current plans also include a financial plan covering the period up to 2028. The financial expenditure primarily affects OPERAS Services, which is why coordination with WP5 was important, but the tasks for which the National Nodes are to be responsible were also taken into account; accordingly, there was an intensive exchange with WP7.

Task 2.3 – Human resources

The question of how the research infrastructure presents itself as an employer was extremely important. In order to cope with the ever-growing tasks at OPERAS, specialists had to be hired to form a coherent team for the day-to-day business of the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT). In order to create the legal and organisational framework for these employees, it was essential to develop a human resources policy. This was also part of the required professionalisation with regard to ERIC status. This included legal, financial (especially tax) and organisational aspects, as well as binding measures for equal opportunity employment.

Task 2.4 – Strategy implementation plan

The Strategy Implementation Plan deals with the concrete implementation of the strategic goals that have been set. It is also intended to ensure that long-term goals are not lost sight of in day-to-day operations. At the same time, it helps to make the individual goals verifiable by means of appropriate key performance indicators. The plan itself helps to guide the research infrastructure as a whole, and is used in particular by the OCT. This approach, like the results of the other tasks, was the subject of ongoing discussions within the OPERAS committees. This demonstrated the close connection to the tasks of WP3.

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C. Work Package 3: Member States / Associated Countries & other OPERAS stakeholders engagement

The aim of the WP was to make cooperation within OPERAS more efficient. This initially applied to all OPERAS bodies, i.e. the EA as the central body for day-to-day operations, the General Assembly (GA) as the decision-making body, in which the ministries are also represented, and then the Assembly of the Commons (AoC) as the plenary assembly of all OPERAS members, as well as the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) as an advisory body and the OPERAS Special Interest Groups (SIGs). In addition, the interaction between all stakeholder groups within the infrastructure was to be improved, which primarily involved reviewing the efficiency of communication channels and exchange formats.

WP leader: Jisc.

Contributors: MWS, AMU, OPERAS, UNIZD, IBL PAN, UC, OAPEN, UNITO, EKT, ZRC SAZU.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D3.1: Report on the activities of OPERAS bodies

D3.2: Dashboard of activities of the OPERAS different bodies and assemblies

D3.3: Draft statutes of the OPERAS ERIC

Milestone:

MS4: Assembly of Commons

Deviations

From M1-M12: No deviations.

From M13-M36: No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 3.1 – Support to the SIGs and AoC

The task focused on supporting the SIGs and the AoC, which is formed from the SIGs, according to the current governance structure. These stakeholders are particularly important for OPERAS's external image, and they are also relatively distant from the day-to-day and project work of the research infrastructure. The aim was therefore to bring them closer to the ongoing discussions. The Strategy Implementation Plan was presented at the AoC meetings and the implementation of the annual goals set out in it was discussed. A separate roadmap which is updated annually and linked to the

OPERAS Strategic Plan was initiated for the Special Interest Groups. This allowed for better coordination of the SIGs' activities, and there were also joint activities between them. In addition, there were Mutual Learning Exercises, which also promoted exchange among the SIGs and at the same time sensitised the SIGs to how their work could better serve the general goals of OPERAS. The SIGs themselves are characterised by a high degree of flexibility; as part of the activities, consultations (and in coordination with the Executive Assembly) led to the formation of a new SIG for Artificial Intelligence (AI SIG).

Task 3.2 – Support to the GA and the BGR

This task initially supported the GA. As the representatives of the ministries are involved here, the establishment of the Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) as a new form of ministerial participation added a new area of responsibility for this task. How the BGR should be structured was an issue that was pursued in close coordination with T2.1.

Task 3.3 – Support to the SAC

With the SAC, this task was responsible for the central advisory body that provides independent external expertise for the research infrastructure. The monthly meetings were mostly devoted to current OPERAS projects and issues. Discussions included a white paper by the Business Model SIG on 'Collaborative models for OA book publishers', the role of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in the context of open science, and various aspects of multilingualism in science communication. However, the SAC was also encouraged to reflect on its own role within OPERAS and to rethink its activities. This was appropriate because there had been personnel changes in the SAC and a new chair had been elected.

Task 3.4 – Support to the EA

The support of the EA helped this central decision-making body of OPERAS (in accordance with the current pre-ERIC governance) to address the question of how to better organise the responsibilities of this body. In view of the growing tasks and expectations, it was essential to extend the monthly meetings and to include fixed reporting items on specific topics in the agenda, such as reporting and discussing the work of other bodies (SAC, SIGs, National Nodes). Working with the EA certainly led to further structuring of its work and greater professionalism. Ultimately, however, these efforts also demonstrated the need to establish a new form of governance for OPERAS, as outlined in WP2 for the status of the ERIC. The practice of T3.4 thus confirmed these concepts.

D. Work Package 4: OPERAS Innovation Lab development

This WP has established the OPERAS Innovation Lab as the knowledge hub for the OPERAS community. The stakeholders of this WP are partners inside the OPERAS

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community, but also experts from the outside who wish to connect to these endeavours and liaise with OPERAS. In particular, other e-infrastructure providers were among the target groups. The main goal was to gather these stakeholders who could contribute to the development of innovative and FAIR services for the OPERAS community. At the core of the WP was the Innovation Observatory, a central knowledge platform for the OPERAS community. In order to support innovation the WP provided recommendations for implementing FAIR principles and settling sustainability issues. Another challenge the WP has tackled was the often perceived lack of prestige innovative outputs usually face. Here the evaluation framework was set up to gather and develop guidelines for evaluating innovative outputs.

WP leader: IBL PAN.

Contributors: AMU, UNIZD, Jisc, OAPEN, UNITO, DARIAH.

Time frame: M3 to M36.

Deliverables:

D4.1: Guidelines on publishing and evaluating innovative outputs in social sciences and humanities

Milestone:

MS7: Community validation workshop

Deviations

From M1-M12: No deviations.

From M13-M36: No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 4.1 – Innovation observatory

Led by IBL PAN, the WP launched the Innovation Observatory, which provides an overview of relevant practices, initiatives and projects that all showed innovative potential. Specifically, this was done through blog posts written by various contributors, including WP partners and external contributions. The texts were subject to a peer review process and are therefore of high quality. Contacts with innovative stakeholders and their ideas were established through events, mostly virtual, but some also in person. Overall, this work developed very dynamically and brought together many suggestions and ideas. In this way, the Observatory has established itself as a renowned platform for the exchange of innovative formats, thereby also contributing to the external impact of OPERAS in general.

Task 4.2 – Support for innovative outputs

Support for innovative outputs also benefited from the Observatory's successes. This is because the information on innovation supplemented the case studies, which

benefited the guidelines for the life cycle of innovations and innovative results ([D4.1](#)). A separate workflow was developed here to enable the systematic processing and evaluation of relevant innovative case studies.

Task 4.3 – Evaluation framework for innovative outputs

The development of the evaluation framework was driven forward in close coordination with T4.2. Based on the same case studies as in the previous task, external experts were consulted who, based on the available material, presented appropriate evaluation criteria for the evaluation of new innovative results. Different professional communities were also taken into account here. The results were also made available in the Observatory under the [Innovation Lab case study](#).

E. Work Package 5: Technical Support to OPERAS Services

The WP was responsible for the further development of OPERAS Services. The aim was to further expand and enrich the service catalogue of the research infrastructure, always taking into account the FAIR principles. In a further step, the connection to infrastructures at the European level was completed, in particular SSHOC and OpenAIRE ([EOSC marketplace](#)). Since OPERAS operates as a distributed infrastructure, linking it to the catalogues was an important step towards stabilising the service offering. This task was carried out continuously throughout the project, while the technical development and completion of further services took place during the first project phase (M1-M12).

WP leader: OPERAS.

Contributors: AMU, UC, OAPEN, LEXIS, NET7, UP.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D5.1: OPERAS Initial technical design

D5.2: Metrics Service TRL9

D5.3: Publishing Service Portal TRL9

D5.4: Certification Service TRL9

D5.5: Design components architecture to support the translation platform

D5.6: OPERAS final technical design

Milestone:

MS9: OPERAS Portfolio

Deviations

From M1-M12: D5.2 “Metrics Service”, D5.3 “Pathfinder Service” and D5.4 “Certification Service” were due 31 August 2023 and have been timely submitted on 20 August 2023.

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As their original titles have been revised according to the AMD01, all three deliverables have been reopened for renaming.

From M13-M36: No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 5.1 – Structuration of OPERAS portfolio and catalogues of services

The establishment of a service management system was crucial for the development and partial reorganisation of the OPERAS service catalogue. Life cycle management for the services is particularly important for the long-term maintenance of the service catalogue. It also simplifies continuous connection and collaboration with the EOSC marketplace. The task itself lasted for the entire duration of the project and included three examples in tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 to establish the processes in this service management. Finally, the design study for a multilingual translation service that can be used in collaborative scenarios in a scientific environment was completed.

Task 5.2 – Technical development for OPERAS Metrics Service

Task 5.2 focused on the OPERAS Metrics Service. Previously available in beta version, it has now been completed under the direction of Ubiquity Press (UP) and is ready for full deployment. This required updating and reprogramming the code used. Further work focused on user-friendliness in order to facilitate the acceptance of this service and its use on other platforms. This included not only corresponding adjustments to the tool itself, but also appropriate documentation. The concrete application of the Metrics Service and how external users can use the tool was another task in WP6, with which there was close exchange.

Task 5.3 – Technical development for OPERAS Publishing Service Portal

A similar process was adopted for the completion of the OPERAS Publication Service Portal, which was led by NET7 and supported by LEXIS. Specifically, the database structure was adapted and the code further developed. The main goal here was to create a common access point for users. As an OPERAS Pathfinder Service, the service is now up and running.

Task 5.4 – Technical development for OPERAS Certification Service

Originally launched as a certification service, it was put into operation as the OPERAS PRISM Peer Review service. At the heart of PRISM, which is maintained by DOAB as part of the distributed infrastructure of OPERAS, are criteria for peer review procedures that make quality checks transparent. In this respect, PRISM is not concerned with validating scientific content per se, but rather with making visible the process that aims to check the quality of scientific output.

Task 5.5 – Design study for OPERAS Translation Service

The plan was to conduct a design study for a collaborative and multilingual translation tool based on open source and cloud technology. Under the leadership of the University

of Coimbra (UC), MONDAECUS was created, a platform that is already ready for use. Designed as an open and inclusive service for translating scholarly content in the SSH, MONDAECUS engages academic and non-academic communities through co-creation, peer collaboration, and transparent revision workflows. Initial tests have been very promising, so this translation platform is likely to become an important part of the OPERAS service catalogue in the foreseeable future.

E. Work Package 6: User Engagement and Training

The WP aimed to develop a systematic and methodologically validated framework for the continuous evaluation of user behaviour in OPERAS services. The approach was strictly user-oriented and took into account a wide range of criteria that determine user behaviour, such as expectations of the services, their availability and satisfaction with them. Furthermore, the WP also focused on the development of a training framework for open scholarly communication. Various factors were taken into account in these tasks, such as multiculturalism, multilingualism and FAIR principles. Overall, these measures contributed to making OPERAS services more sustainable. The user perspective was a particularly important criterion here, as it leads to greater acceptance in scholarly communities. The individual tasks built on each other, giving the WP a very methodically structured process

WP leader: UNIZD.

Contributors: AMU, OPERAS, UC, OAPEN, UNITO, LEXIS, UP.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D6.1: Common framework defining the methodology for achieving user-centred quality objectives

D6.2: Report on implementation of the methodological framework for user-centred quality on selected services

D6.3: Framework for the development of open science and scholarly communication training

Milestones:

MS6: First-draft of the methodological framework for achieving user-centred quality objectives of OPERAS services

MS10: Test implementation of user-centred quality evaluation on selected services

Deviations

From M1-M12: No deviations.

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From M13-M36: No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 6.1 – Identification of relevant services and targeted user groups

The task was to identify the services and their relevant user groups so that it was clear which target groups should be addressed for specific services. This was a prerequisite for the following tasks, but was also closely related to the services that were developed in parallel in WP5 (especially T5.2, T5.3 and T5.4). Since this approach was essentially important for the entire OPERAS community, OPERAS, as a project partner, led this task to ensure prompt communication.

Task 6.2 – Developing common methodological framework for achieving user-centred quality objectives of OPERAS services

The next step was to develop a framework for ongoing evaluation based on user-defined requirements. The broad User Centred Design approach was chosen as the starting point because it covered the entire design cycle, from identifying and analysing user goals and needs in relation to existing or planned services to providing ongoing recommendations on usability and evaluating the design. The results were documented in the ‘Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives’ (D6.2).

Task 6.3 – Implementation of the developed framework on selected services

The framework was then tested on selected services (including GoTriple, Pathfinder, and GraspOS). The main criteria here were usability, accessibility, and user experience. The tests were carried out with different stakeholder groups, including early career researchers (doctoral students, postdocs), librarians, and senior SSH researchers. The practical findings led to further refinement of the methods.

Task 6.4 – OPERAS essential skills and training provision

Finally, Task 6.4 established a training framework to elevate user engagement with OPERAS services, emphasising open science and FAIR principles. This involved a diverse exchange and collaboration with various projects, but also with National Nodes, through which the comprehensive training material could be distributed. Relevant articles and guidelines were also written as documentation. As these activities promoted the acceptance of the services in question, push strategies were also developed to reinforce this effect.

G. Work Package 7: Support to National Nodes

This WP dealt with the implementation of OPERAS National Nodes and the framing of their connection with the central hub. National Nodes play a pivotal role in establishing

a connection point outside of the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services and training. They are in a unique position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level. This strategy is fully aligned with the paths to outreach beyond Europe, and with the development and implementation of the GoTriple platform, benefiting directly from a future service dedicated to supporting translations and stimulating cross-publications.

WP leader: UC.

Contributors: MWS, IBL PAN, UNIZD, Jisc, ZRC SAZU, OPERAS, OAPEN, UNITO, AMU, EKT.

Time frame: M1 to M36.

Deliverables:

D7.2: Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes (M12)

D7.1: Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes (M18)

D7.3: Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes - Final (M33)

Milestone:

MS2: Internal WP Kick-off meeting with prospective National Nodes.

Deviations

From M1-M12: No deviations.

From M13-M36: No deviations.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 7.1 – Support in the building of OPERAS national nodes

Throughout this task, all WP leaders and WP members contributed to the development and implementation of the OPERAS National Nodes, using the effort of the project of gathering the OPERAS Executive Assembly and working on developing the documentation to support shaping each node. In this sense, the task has successfully delivered D7.2 "Roadmap for the implementation of the OPERAS National Nodes", at M12, in time. The roadmap for the implementation of OPERAS National Nodes provided a first approach for the work that would continue to be developed throughout the following months of the project, establishing a strategy, requirements and metrics for implementing the nodes.

The task has also been responsible for putting together the WP milestone, the internal kick-off meeting, which was held online and has been effective in aggregating efforts to the planning of the work of the project.

As a permanent task of the project, it has also provided support to the other

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deliverables in this WP.

Task 7.2 – Aligning the governance between the National Nodes and the central hub

The task focused on compiling information to better align the legal and contractual relations between the Nodes and OPERAS Research Infrastructure. During the task, discussions were held on the options for organising the governance of each node, with OPERAS providing support for the different realities of the nodes. Support was also given to the nodes to provide basic templates of documents to be shared and used in the national context (e.g. a model for a Memorandum of Understanding between the nodes and their national partners). *D7.1: Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes*, expanded the comprehension about the reality of each node and further explored challenges and opportunities for their development, giving a sound continuity for the work of the group.

Task 7.3 – Connecting OPERAS with other national and international Social Sciences and Humanities nodes

The task encompassed a series of actions in order to realise the connection of the OPERAS nodes with other national and international infrastructures. During the period, task members have developed documentation and provided support for expansion of the nodes networks, which was successfully achieved. The task has also leveraged on the regular meetings of the project and the National Nodes Committee to reach a next level of organisation of activities, with the official creation of a shared online folder and a shared document with yearly plans for the Nodes. Towards the end of the project, all 13 Executive Assembly members had defined at least a group of activities or a robust strategy, depending on their national realities and funding availability outside the project. Task 7.3 has also been active and a protagonist in the update of the National Nodes Roadmap, contributing strongly to the delivery of the D7.3 report, Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes – Final (M33). The final document resulted in a much detailed and refined value proposition.

H. Work Package 8: Communication and Impact Assessment

This work package was a critical element in the further development of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. During its activities, it has facilitated the bidirectional communication flow to and from external communities and partners. The WP provided tools needed both to communicate OPERAS achievements and to receive the vital information necessary to adapt and adjust the strategy and activities of the Research Infrastructure, as well as to support the OPERAS services (WP5), the National Nodes (WP7) and the Innovation Lab (WP4). The WP was also naturally connected to all other WPs and OPERAS bodies, facilitating exchange and the flow of information throughout the RI.

WP leader: MWS

Contributors: UC, OPERAS, all

Time frame: M1-M36

Deliverables:

D8.1 - Communication Strategy and Toolkit

D8.2 - Impact Monitoring Dashboard

D8.3 - Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

D8.4 - Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results - Update

D8.5 - Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results - Final

D8.6 - Communication Strategy and Toolkit - Final

D8.7 - Impact Monitoring Dashboard - Final

Milestones:

MS8 - International Conference Organisation

Deviations

From M1-M12:

The delivery of D8.1 “Communication Strategy and Toolkit” and D8.3 “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results” (moved from M5 to M6 according to AMD01), some weeks later than planned, represented a deviation from the initial timeline and was communicated to the Project Officer in advance. This delay was due to the review process taking slightly longer than expected during the winter holiday season, as well as internal adjustments and coordination among consortium partners to ensure all contributions were accurately included. It did not affect any activities of the project.

From M13-M36:

Late Delivery and Postpone of Deliverable: The deliverable D8.4 “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results – Update” was delivered 2½ months later than the due date due to the need to incorporate updated project results, recent feedback from consortium partners, and additional inputs from newly conducted dissemination activities.

The deliverable D8.5 “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results - Final” was postponed by approximately three months, from M30 to M33. The time span between D8.4 and D8.5 proved too short to allow for substantial progress or the inclusion of significant new results. In order to ensure that the final version could provide a more comprehensive and meaningful overview, the deadline was therefore extended. This adjustment was made in close coordination with the European Commission project officer.

Change of Social Media Channels: During the project period, the development of the social media platform **X** (formerly Twitter) took a direction that diverged significantly from OPERAS’ core values as a distributed research infrastructure committed to trust, open scholarly communication, and supporting access to research in the social

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sciences and humanities. In light of these developments, the OPERAS Coordination Team, with a clear vote from the Executive Assembly, decided to withdraw from the platform in January 2025. A detailed statement on this decision is available here: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/8559>. Instead, OPERAS opened a new channel on Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/operaseu.bsky.social>. Fortunately, that did not affect the achievement of the Key Performance Indicator (KPIs) promised in the Grant Agreement, as they had already been reached at that stage.

Explanation of the work carried out per task

Task 8.1 – Communication and outreach

During this task, which was developed throughout the project, the WP team has established a strong communication presence via its channels, such as the [website](#), [blog](#), and social media ([X](#) until January 2025, [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), [YouTube](#), [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#)) presence as well as the OPERAS [newsletter](#), developing a steady exchange with the OPERAS community and stakeholders. All communication channels were updated and refreshed in terms of design and appearance throughout the project period. Different campaigns were carried out, including those for the OPERAS Conference, the Science Summit, the OPERAS service GoTriple, and a Retrospective of 2024. Presentations at international conferences were given by the entire project consortium, and webinars about OPERAS were organised, such as those on the new Open Access Books SIG, the OPERAS service Pathfinder, and the Open Chat Series of the Advocacy SIG. All these activities were supported and promoted by the communication team.

This task was also responsible for the delivery of the two versions of the Communication Strategy, in Months 5 and 36. The first version helped to establish communication activities within OPERAS-PLUS, as well as a clear strategy for leading them. The final version is a report on the further development of this strategy, including a record of all activities undertaken during the project's development and future plans for communication within OPERAS.

Inside this task, the team has also developed MS8 - International Conference Organisation, the [OPERAS Conference 2024](#), which took place in April 2024 in Zadar, Croatia and gathered around 150 researchers and open science advocates to discuss topics related to open scholarly communication and equitable publishing. Several communication materials were also produced and created within the task, including logos for the project & National Nodes, a new OPERAS corporate design, presentation and document templates, flyers, policy briefs, and videos - all gathered in a communication toolkit. Since 2025, a press release template (e.g., https://operas.hypotheses.org/files/2025/06/2025_04_Press-release_OPERAS-Annual-Report-2024-published.pdf) has been introduced, enabling a more consistent and aligned way of sharing information while also providing a better overview of all press releases. Further enhancements of the website also took place. In addition, a SWOT analysis and OPERAS Personas for communication were prepared. Furthermore, the exchange and communication alignment with and for National Nodes was strengthened by offering dedicated communication workshops and disseminating news to the national nodes in

a more structured way. National Node interviews have therefore been conducted to gain a better understanding of the needs of the national communities and National Nodes of OPERAS.

It can be stated that all KPIs have been achieved and in some cases exceeded. A detailed list can be found in deliverable 8.6 in Section 5, and in particular the development of the indicators during the project period in figures in Section 5.2. OPERAS gained steadily growing interest. For example, during the project period, the subscriber base for the newsletter increased by 62.92%, and visits to the website rose by 37.54% when comparing the first project year to the last.

Task 8.2 – Impact monitoring and assessment The task has worked throughout the duration of the project to first define and later refine and implement a list of metrics and KPIs to monitor OPERAS performance and assess its impact.

The task team has first defined a set of metrics, KPIs and case studies for the performance monitoring and the impact assessment, which were presented in the first version of the deliverable – *Impact Monitoring Dashboard (D8.2)*, at Month 12.

During the following project period the KPIs have been adjusted and also the data of OPERAS has been evaluated and a base was created and data collection better structured. The work culminated in the development of the Performance Monitoring and Impact Monitoring Dashboard within Google Looker Studio (see: <https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/90b8234b-460b-4b7b-9974-232fec6953f4?hl=en>) which was officially published at the end of the project, together with the delivery of *D8.7 - Impact monitoring dashboard - Final*. The deliverable outlines methodological refinements inspired by the ESFRI policy brief on the *Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures*, see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8091633>, updates KPIs to reflect strategic shifts, and describes the technical and organisational process of developing the final dashboard. The work carried out within the task has matured to improve informed decision-making through visual, accessible, and regularly updated data, while also strengthening the infrastructure's strategic alignment with Open Science principles.

Originally, the task was planned only to create a dashboard for impact monitoring. However, under constant review and following the suggestion of the ESFRI policy brief, it was decided to extend the dashboard to include an additional performance monitoring dashboard, to better align with strategic objectives. This part of the dashboard is for now only accessible by the Executive Assembly and OPERAS coordination team. It is planned to make this part of the dashboard also accessible to everyone (a decision of the OPERAS Executive Assembly is expected in September). The dashboard will also be embedded in the future update of the website in Q4 of 2025.

Furthermore, additional case studies, which are incorporated into the impact monitoring dashboard, have also been conducted within the task.

Task 8.3 – Dissemination and exploitation

The task has developed an internal marketing analysis of the OPERAS services, putting

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together a permanent effort to sustain and further exploit OPERAS services catalogue, in conjunction with WP5. The task has developed and delivered the three versions of the Plan of Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), ensuring future sustainability and exploitation of project results, especially considering OPERAS' pathway towards an ERIC. A dedicated table of dissemination measures including the target audience and means of dissemination have been a solid foundation for disseminating the project results. For the exploitation and use of results in further research and innovation activities, five KER Champions for OPERAS-PLUS have been developed, are being reported on, and have their measures adjusted across the different deliverables. All project deliverables and presentations during the project period of OPERAS-PLUS have been uploaded to [OPERAS Zenodo Community](#).

IV. Impact

The aim of OPERAS-PLUS was to further prepare the research infrastructure on the path to becoming an ERIC. First, the measures pursued the development of the internal organisation in terms of improved efficiency and coherence, while also focusing on the emerging transformation of governance as required for an ERIC. Second, the service catalogue was a central focus. The services offered had to be consolidated technically, but also evaluated in terms of user-friendliness and applicability (training) and prepared with a view to future developments and innovations.

Against this background, the following aspects should be highlighted. They clearly show the effects of the project on the OPERAS Research Infrastructure:

-The creation of the BGR as a new body is a central component of the transformation to an ERIC, as it significantly improves ministerial involvement. This also includes the new membership structure, in particular the newly created 'mandated organisation' membership type. This simplifies measures of financial consolidation of OPERAS as a whole.

-The dashboard of activities of OPERAS bodies will now make it much easier to understand how the various bodies and stakeholder groups of OPERAS operate and what activities they undertake. This establishes a tool that improves internal communication within the infrastructure.

-The National Nodes are now an integral part of OPERAS' overall strategy. For the existing nodes, their activities can be much better coordinated with the Central Hub, and their country-specific characteristics can also be better taken into account. With the help of the strategy for the National Nodes, it is now also easier to support the nodes that are currently in the making.

-The Innovation Lab has created conditions for better identifying the needs of the OPERAS community. This allows the requirements for possible new services to be derived in a targeted manner. Agreements and exchange formats with approaches in other countries are also developing promisingly. For example, a connection has been established to the Innovation Lab for "[Servicestelle für Diamond Open Access](#)" (SeDOA), which is the single point of contact for Diamond Open Access publishing in Germany. This also demonstrates the effective exchange with the National Node.

-A number of services have been renewed or have been brought to the phase of

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production and the service portfolio has been brought to a new level. Overall, the life cycle of the various services can now be monitored very well, which is a great relief for the maintenance and further development of the service catalogue, especially given the principle of distributed services.

-The methodological foundations for a training framework have been laid for the use and application of the services, and training materials have been provided in accordance with the FAIR principles. These materials take the user perspective into account, are quality-oriented and help in their own way to disseminate the services and stabilise the research infrastructure.

-The two dashboards are also very helpful, one for the activities of the OPERAS bodies and, above all, the impact monitoring dashboard for OPERAS. This facilitates the targeted distribution of information within the OPERAS research infrastructure and has also made the dissemination of news to the community much clearer. Furthermore, it allows the OPERAS bodies and public to assess the impact of OPERAS as a research infrastructure constantly.

These examples illustrate how much the key exploitable results of the individual WPs contribute to the internal consolidation of OPERAS-PLUS and thus promote the maturity of the research infrastructure.

The next steps for the further development of OPERAS towards an ERIC have also been planned. The OPERAS-PLUS project has made decisive progress in the construction phase (since 2022) towards becoming an ERIC, paving the way for the final preparations scheduled in the follow-up project OPERAS-PRIME. The preliminary work provides very good conditions for this.